

Flavivaccine

Safely protecting against
mosquito-borne viral diseases

We aim to deliver a **safe and cost-effective** vaccine against diseases resulting from mosquito-borne flavivirus infections, such as dengue, yellow fever, Zika and West Nile viruses.

RISING MOSQUITO-BORNE PANDEMIC THREATS DUE TO CLIMATE CHANGE AND HUMAN-LED ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT

- **500 mil** Infections per year
- **>100.000** Annual deaths
- **€9 bil** Economic loss (For dengue virus only)

■ 1 Flavivaccine

Our novel approach enables the **targeting of multiple flaviviruses with a single vaccine**, thereby **lifting the burden from healthcare systems**. This solution has **multi-market potential**, serving both as a **travel and epidemic/pandemic response strategy**.

FIND OUT MORE

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